

A New Monohedral Tiling by a Non-Convex Pentagon

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Abstract

I present a monohedral tiling of the Euclidean plane by a new non-convex pentagon. The tiling uses only orientation-preserving isometries—translations and half-turns (180° rotations)—and no reflections are required. A unique strip structure is forced by local matching around the single concave vertex. Extending the strips yields a full tiling of the plane. To the best of my knowledge, this polygon and tiling have not previously been documented [1].

1 Definition of the Polygon

Let $P = (v_0, v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4)$ be the pentagon listed in counterclockwise order with:

$$\begin{aligned}v_0 &= (0, 0), \\v_1 &= (2.6641, 0), \\v_2 &= (1.6920, 0.61001), \\v_3 &= (1.8747, 1.7321), \\v_4 &= (0.4267, 1.7321).\end{aligned}$$

There is a unique concave vertex at v_2 (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Polygon P with labeled vertices.

2 Forced Local Matching

Edges near the concave vertex form a tooth-and-notch pattern that allows a valid match only by a half-turn (180° rotation) about the midpoint of v_2v_3 (Figure 2). No reflections can satisfy these matching constraints [2].

3 Strip Structure and Tiling

By repeating the half-turn matching, a forced infinite strip is generated (Figure 3). Adjacent strips interlock by a unique translation, producing a full tiling of the plane (Figure 4).

Figure 2: Local matching at the concave vertex v_2 . Only the half-turn produces a valid fit.

Figure 3: Strip formed by successive half-turns.

4 Conclusion

This work demonstrates a new monohedral tiling by a non-convex pentagon that requires no reflections. The forced strip structure leads to a unique tiling. This contributes to the incomplete classification of monohedral tilings by non-convex polygons.

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References

- [1] B. Grünbaum and G. C. Shephard, *Tilings and Patterns*, W.H. Freeman, 1987.
- [2] C. Goodman-Strauss, *Open Questions in Tiling Theory*, arXiv preprint.

Figure 4: Full tiling of the plane.